

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

A review study for Toxocariasis

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Abstract

Many researchers reported rates of infected dogs with *T. canis* and cats with *Toxocara cati* all over the world. The degree of tissue damage in the host and the concomitant elicitation of signs and symptoms are varied in different invaded tissues. The liver, lungs and central nervous system, including the eyes, are considered the most sensitive organs. In addition, the number of migrating juveniles and the age of the host. Inflammation manifests as eosinophilic granulomas. The immediate hypersensitivity responses to dying and dead larvae in the viscera, including the lungs, liver and brain, produce symptoms characteristic of VLM.

The current review discusses the *Toxocara* sp. infection from the historical background, taxonomy, lifecycle, pathogenesis, clinical signs, epidemiology, diagnosis, control and treatment. And provides an overview of existing literature and data on the *Toxocaraiasis* with their references.

Keywords: *Toxocara canis*; *Toxocara cati*; Disease; Dogs; Cats

1. Introduction

1.1. Historical background of *Toxocara canis*

In the past century, Nutall and Strickland [1] examined dogs in Cambridge- England, they identified *T. canis*.

Human infection with *Toxocariasis* was first described by Wilder [2]. The latter he identified a nematode larva of unknown species within a retinal granuloma of a child. Subsequently, similar cases were reported considered the connection between Toxocariasis and dogs was established. In 1952, [3] reported similar cases in a series of children suffered high circulating eosinophilia and severe, long-term, multisystem disease. From this group of patients, they described most of the clinical features of VLM and in histopathological sections of tissues obtained at biopsy, correctly classified the causative agents as the larva of either *T. canis* or *T. cati*. Since that time, the juveniles of these two parasite species have been detected in a variety of lesions of the eye and throughout the body [4, 5] in patients in different part of the world.

1.2. Taxonomy

The Taxonomy of *Toxocara* sp. was according to [6]:

Kingdom: Animalia

Phylum: Nematoda

Class: Secernentea

Order: Ascaridida

Family: Toxocaridae

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Genus: *Toxocara* (Stiles, 1905)
= *Belascaris* (Leiper, 1907)
= *Neoascaris* (Travassos, 1927)
= *Toxocara* (Ranther, 1930)

1.3. Life cycle of *Toxocara* sp.

When a *Toxocara canis* egg hatches inside a dog's stomach, the larva invades the bowel wall and arrives in a pulmonary capillary; it is considerably more prone to remain in the circulation than to break into the alveolus, especially if its host is a mature dog. If the larva fails to enter the alveolus, it will be returned to the heart by pulmonary veins and carried away by the systemic circulation, perhaps to lodge in the kidney or some other somatic tissue, where it will encyst as an arrested infective larva [7]. The most important arrested larvae of *T. canis* are those to be found in the tissues of the female dog. Transmission of infection from bitch to pups occurs almost exclusively by way of transplacental transmission. During the last trimester of pregnancy, arrested larvae are reactivated and migrate from the tissues of the bitch to the pups in utero [8]. After parturition, small numbers of reactivated larvae also may be shed in the milk.

1.4. Pathogenesis

The degree of tissue damage in the host and the concomitant elicitation of signs and symptoms are varied in different invaded tissues. The liver [9], lungs [10] and central nervous system (CNS) [11], including the eyes [12], are considered the most sensitive organs. In addition, the number of migrating juveniles and the age of the host are two additional factors important as to whether a given individual's condition will become elevated above the clinical horizon. Pathological consequences are largely dependent upon the death of the juveniles. Their death heralds the onset of marked delayed-type and immediate-type hypersensitivity responses. Inflammation manifests as eosinophilic granulomas. The immediate hypersensitivity responses to dying and dead larvae in the viscera, including the lungs, liver and brain, produce symptoms characteristic of VLM. In the eye, migrating third stage larvae can damage the retina, inducing granulomatous reactions leading to impaired sight.

In severe cases, the granuloma was responsible for the loss of sight. These pathological manifestations have, in the past, occasionally been misdiagnosed as retinoblastoma [13, 14]. Today, with reliable immunodiagnostic reagents and methods, OLM is almost never mistaken for other clinical entities. Epidemiologic evidence suggests that ocular disease tends to occur in the absence of systemic involvement and vice versa, which has led to the proposal that the two manifestations of this infection be reclassified as OLM.

Portion of dog small intestine with adult *T. canis* [15]. It is possible that there are strains of *T. canis* with specific tropisms. Alternatively, VLM may reflect the consequences of a host inflammatory response to repeated waves of migrating larvae through the viscera, whereas OLM occurs in individuals who have not been previously sensitized [16].

2. Clinical signs and symptoms

2.1. Clinical Signs of *Toxocara canis* in dogs

Young puppies usually have the most severe signs of toxocariasis. The typical symptoms include poor growth, loss of condition and sometimes an enlarged abdomen (potbelly). Worms may be passed in the feces or vomited. Other possible symptoms are diarrhea, constipation, vomiting, flatulence, coughing or nasal discharge. Chronic enteritis can result in thickening of the intestinal wall or intussusception. In severe cases, puppies may die from obstruction of the gall bladder, bile duct or pancreatic duct or even rupture of the intestine and subsequent peritonitis. Intestinal infections with small numbers of parasites tend to be asymptomatic [7].

The pass invasion of the larvae through the lungs can cause inflammation and producing respiratory distress of varying severity. Pneumonia can be seen soon after birth if the puppy was infected *in utero*. Affected puppies may die within 2 or 3 days after birth. Severe infections can also cause ascites, fatty degeneration of the liver, secondary bacterial pneumonia or chronic stunting. Myocarditis is a rare complication. Symptomatic infections are rare in adult dogs. High levels of liver enzymes may be detected during larval migration and ocular signs, may be observed such as orbital cellulitis and multifocal retinal disease. In sheep dogs, retinal disease is characterized by well-delineated areas of hyper reflectivity in the tapetal fundus, often accompanied by retinal hyperpigmentation and mild vitreal clouding. In severely affected animals, widespread hyperreflectivity and attenuation of the retinal blood vessels have been reported. Most dogs with retinal lesions do not seem to be visually impaired [17].

2.2. Clinical Signs of *Toxocara canis* infection in human

A variety of disease states are described but some symptoms are not well understood and require further elucidation.

2.2.1. Visceral Larva Migrans

The VLM is mainly a disease of young children (5 years old) [18]. The disease manifested with fever; enlargement and necrosis of the liver [19]; enlargement of the spleen; lower respiratory symptoms (particularly bronchospasm, resembling asthma); eosinophilia sometimes raised up to 70% [20] and hypergammaglobulinemia of immunoglobulin M (IgM), IgG, and IgE classes. In the last of these instances, symptoms are more pronounced with increased levels of IgE/anti-IgE immune complexes [19]. Myocarditis [21], nephritis [22] and involvement of the CNS have been described. The involvement of CNS can lead to seizures, neuropsychiatric symptoms, or encephalopathy. There is an increasing appreciation that more subtle clinical manifestations might also arise as a result of long-term exposure to the migrating juveniles. So-called covert toxocariasis ranges in spectrum from asymptomatic infection to larvae migrating in specific target organs [23, 24, 25]. In the lungs, larval migrations may result in asthma [26, 27]. It was suggested that *T. canis* as an environmental risk factor for asthma among some inner-city populations [28]. Similarly, in the brain, *T. canis* has been implicated as one of the causes of so-called idiopathic seizure disorders [29]. One study implicated *Toxocara* as a contributing factor in skin disorders of at least two varieties (prurigo and urticaria) [30]. While another presented indirect evidence linking *Toxocara* infection with a form of eosinophilic arthritis [31]. In experimental infections in mice, learning behavior and memory are affected and both appeared to be dose and time dependent [32]. It is therefore reasonable to speculate that similar phenomena are likely to be at work in long-term infections in humans, as well.

2.2.2. Ocular Larva Migrans

Usually OLM occurs in 5 to 10 years old children and typically presents as unilateral vision impairment that is sometimes accompanied by strabismus [33]. The most serious consequence of the infection is invasion of the retina, leading to granuloma formation, which occurs typically peripherally or in the posterior pole. These granulomas drag the retina and create a distortion, heteropia, or detachment of the macula [34]. The degree of visual acuity impairment depends on the specific area involved and the blindness is common. The OLM can also cause diffuse endophthalmitis or papillitis which can be followed by secondary glaucoma can follow. In at least one rare instance following long-term infection with *Toxocara*, a choroidal neovascular membrane formed after presenting earlier as chorioretinitis [35].

2.2.3. Cutaneous and covert toxocariasis

Two syndromes were described such as, covert toxocariasis and common toxocariasis, which were less typical and not as severe. During the last two decades, cutaneous manifestations such as chronic urticaria, chronic pruritus and miscellaneous eczema, in patients with *Toxocara* antibodies, have been studied by different investigators. In some cases, these cutaneous manifestations were the only signs indicating the presence of the disease and they were cured after antihelmintic treatment when there was good patient compliance. Beatrice [36] focused on these particular skin manifestations regarding their clinical description, diagnosis and treatment.

2.2.4. Nervous toxocariasis

Clinical involvement of the nervous system in visceral larva migrans due to *Toxocara* is rare, although in experimental animals the larvae frequently migrate to the brain. Sandra [37] reviewed the literature in the past five decades to date found only 29 cases of brain involvement in toxocariasis. In 20 cases, various clinical and laboratory manifestations of eosinophilic meningitis, encephalitis, myelitis or radiculopathy were reported. They reported two children with neurological manifestations, in which there was cerebrospinal fluid pleocytosis with marked eosinophilia and a positive serology for *Toxocara* both in serum and CSF. Serology for *Schistosoma mansoni*, *Cysticercus cellulosae* and *Toxoplasma* were negative in CSF, that were sterile in both cases [38].

3. Epidemiology

3.1. Prevalence of *Toxocara canis* in Iraq

The *T. canis* was first recorded in Iraq by Leiper [39]. Other study in Mosul Woodruff [40] recorded 25.5% polluted soil with *T. canis*; were as 25.7% rate of infected dogs recorded by Al-Kalidy [41]. Then, Al-Saqer [42] considered domestic dogs as a reservoir hosts to *T. canis* infection. Subsequently, Sultan [43] showed that infection rate with *T. canis* was up 46% in dogs in Al- Najif province. Then after, in Basrha, Al-Emara [44] found a rate of 35.2% in dogs infected with *T. canis*, and contaminated soil 25% and contaminated gardens grasses 10%. Earth worm was recorded as transmitter to

the *Toxocara* sp. in Baghdad by Hadi & Al- Amery [45]. In Sulaimani province, Bajalan [46] recorded 36% of dogs infected with *T. canis*. Then, in Baghdad province, Hadi [47] found *T. canis* caused highest rate (53.3%) that polluted the Lettuce. In addition of polluted fresh vegetables up to 18.3% [48]. Finally, Hadi & Faraj [49] found high rate 67.5% of *T. canis* in fecal samples of stray dogs in Baghdad province. Hadi and Kawan [50] revealed the total infection rate of *Toxocara canis* 52% in the domestic and stray

4. Diagnosis

4.1. Diagnosis of *Toxocara canis* in dogs

Patent infections in dogs can be diagnosed by fecal flotation technique [51]. In fact, enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) has been used to detect the non-patent infections in dogs [52]. In addition to that, an immunological test (IHAT) was used to diagnose the infection with *T. canis* worms in dogs as definitive host and in mice experimentally infected with second stage larvae of *T. canis* as paratenic host, in Basrah province [53].

Scanning electron microscopy images were scientific photography featuring science were best than the direct photo for adult of *Toxocara* worms [54].

4.2. Immuno-serological techniques for diagnosing human toxocariasis

The excretory- secretory antigens of *T. canis* larvae (TES) are widely used in serodiagnostic tests that are used for both the diagnosis and seroepidemiological studies [55]. These antigens are obtained from *in vitro* maintenance of infective larvae and are a mixture of highly immunogenic glycoproteins [56]. Since the first description of TES antigens production [57], few modifications in the method have been made. Recently, modified protocols for TES antigens production has been reported, increasing the parasite yield up to five fold, improving the larval purity and reducing the execution time of the protocol [58]. The use of validated serodiagnostic tests has provided a good understanding on the prevalence of human exposure to *Toxocara*. Toxocariasis is one of the few human parasitic diseases whose serodiagnosis uses a standardized antigen [59]. Currently, the best serodiagnostic options are using the ELISA-IgG as a screening test and confirm any positive serum with an immunoblot test.

4.3. Enzyme linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA)

Human toxocariasis is most often a benign, asymptomatic and self-limiting disease, as long as re-infection does not occur. Until moment, the ELISA assay is the most widely accepted serodiagnostic test for the detection of anti-*Toxocara* IgG antibodies. Although the ELISA may detect infections by both *T. canis* and *T. cati* [60]. A positive result in a serological test does not necessarily indicate a causative relationship between *Toxocara* infection and current disease [61]. Probably, a mixture of recombinant antigens will improve the efficacy of the immunoassays [62]. Hadi, [63] revealed to ELISA human IgG tests for *T. canis* were done on 92 serum samples taken from 22 healthy and 70 hospitalized patients with eye conditions randomly in Baghdad city. Of the 22 healthy persons, 4 were positive and of 70 patients, 15 were positive accounting for a prevalence of 18.18% and 21.42%, respectively.

4.4. Molecular diagnosis

Investigations into the molecular biology of *Toxocara* have mainly focused on the secreted proteins of the migrating juvenile stages. These proteins have proven useful in immunodiagnosis of VLM, and OLM. Speculation favors these same proteins in aiding the worm regarding its capacity to evade potentially protective immune responses. This idea derives from the fact that the juvenile stage wanders about the tissues for months to years without apparent interference from the host. Presumably, the worms eventually die of old age.

The fact that many of the excretory-secretory proteins from the juvenile stages constitute a family of at least six highly antigenic mucins [64] associated with the cuticular surface reinforces this concept [65]. Secreted mucins temporarily coat the surface of the worm [66] and are shed into the host periodically [67]. It is thought that this shedding behavior represents an attempt on the part of the parasite to confuse the host's immune system, leaving behind it a trail of slime, not unlike that of a snail [68]. Cathepsin-z-like protease genes have been cloned and their cDNAs have been sequenced, identifying a cysteine protease coding region expressed both in the adult and infective larva [69].

Molecular vaccines could prove useful in aiding in the control of infection in domestic dogs and cats. The search so far has identified the myosins of *Toxocara* as potential candidates [70].

Polymerase chain reaction (PCR)-based methods for *Toxocara* identification in clinical and environmental samples have been described [71], but are not widely available. These methods should provide useful tools for the diagnosis and molecular epidemiological investigations of toxocariasis [72]. Hadi and Kawan, [50] reported the development of sensitive and specific PCR assay allowing rapid and reliable identification of *T. canis* by the fragment size amplified was 380 bp in ITS-2 gene.

5. Prevention and control

5.1. Treatment

5.1.1. In dogs

Owing to the transplacental transmission, unless heroic measure have been taken to prevent infection, pups may be assume to be infected. Medication should start routinely as early as the second week of life and repeated every two weeks until the pup is three month old. Young puppies are also regularly treated with piperazine compounds, which is considered safe and highly effective against ascarids in the lumen of the alimentary tract and therefore ideally suited to removing *Toxocara canis* as they arrive and develop in the intestinal lumens of perinatally infected pups. Puppies over 6 weeks in age can be treated with fenbendazole or ivermectine with pyrantel pamoate. At 8 weeks the formulation of ivermectin with pyrantel pamoate and praziquantel is labeled for use in puppies [7].

5.1.2. In human

Anthelmintic drugs can be used to treat severe visceral larva migrans. Treatment may lead to severe hypersensitivity reactions caused by dying larvae, and anti-inflammatory medications such as corticosteroids are often given concurrently. Treatment of ocular disease may include surgery, laser photocoagulation, and/or drugs to decrease further damage to the eye [38].

6. Control measurements

6.1. Avoiding infection with eggs

Prevention of human infections depends on the treatment and prevention of *Toxocara* infections in animals, the removal of feces before the eggs can become embryonated, good hygiene and public education. To reduce human exposure, puppies and kittens should be dewormed [38].

Adult animals may also need to be treated for patent infections. Canine feces should be removed from areas where children play before the eggs become embryonated [46]. The feces should be burned, buried, or bagged and disposed of in the trash. There is no practical way to remove eggs from the soil once contamination has occurred. Contamination can be decreased in public areas by restrictions on uncontrolled dogs and cats, collection of feces by dog owners, and prevention of animal access to areas such as children's playgrounds. Puppies from 3 weeks to 3 months old excrete large numbers of *T. canis* eggs and appear to be the greatest hazard to humans, [7].

6.1.1. Cleaning measures

Good hygiene can help prevent infections or severe disease. Hands and raw foods should be washed before eating. Children should be taught not to eat soil, and to wash their hands after playing with pets or outdoor activities. Children should not be allowed to play in areas where animal feces are found. Families may also consider postponing the acquisition of a new pet until children are past the toddler stage [38].

7. Conclusion

Human Toxocariasis was caused by ingestion the eggs of *Toxocara canis* or *T. cati* accidentally. The Visceral Larva Migrans VLM is a disease manifested with fever; enlargement and necrosis of the liver; enlargement of the spleen; lower respiratory symptoms (particularly bronchospasm, resembling asthma). Second: The Ocular Larva Migrans OLM occurs in 5 to 10 years old children and typically presents as unilateral vision impairment that is sometimes accompanied by strabismus. The Cutaneous toxocariasis such as chronic urticaria, chronic pruritus and miscellaneous eczema, in patients with *Toxocara* antibodies, have been studied by different investigators. The Nervous toxocariasis such as various clinical and laboratory manifestations of eosinophilic meningitis, encephalitis, myelitis or radiculopathy were

reported. A variety of disease states are described but some symptoms are not well understood and require further elucidation.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing Financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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